

Project plan:
“Matters of Research Assessment and its Implementation”

Subproject: Implementation (MAI-I)

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NOTE:

This is a living document that is updated regularly.

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Content

1. Background

This project plan builds on the joint project application of the Robert K. Merton-Zentrum für Wissenschaftsforschung at the Humboldt-University and the BIH QUEST Center for Responsible Research at Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin to the BUA Objective 3 (authors: Cornelia Schendzielorz, HU and Miriam Kip, BIH QUEST Center, submitted for review: July 2022, approval after review: October 2022). This project plan describes the subproject “implementation” (MAI-I). The project plan is a living document and updated according to the actual course of the project.

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Existing systems of research assessment no longer do justice to current requirements and developments in research itself, but also society, such as digitalization, diversification of research tasks and career paths, or the emergence of new formats of research outputs and application models. This misalignment is subject to different national as well as international initiatives that aim to reform the current research assessment systems in alignment with responsible research and innovation (RRI) and open sciences practices. These include for example the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment – CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) (2022), the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021, 2022), or the recommendations by the German Research Foundation (DFG) on the status of publications in research assessment (2022) as well as the DFG position paper on Open Science (2023).

2. Aims

The project aims to develop a common understanding and guidance on how the current developments in research assessment and the principles should and can be transferred into practice at the BUA. The project focuses on research assessments of individual researchers during appointments of professors and tenure track evaluations. The project seeks to develop and implement responsible research assessment strategies and tools that reflect the different goals of the four BUA partners and at the same time map and create synergies and common features for the shared research space. The overarching project goal is to equip BUA organizations in their strategic planning and to promote participatory alignment with organizational governance processes, infrastructures and practices so as to implement and embed RRI and open science research assessments into institutional infrastructures and organizational practices for appointments. By doing so, we aim to increase the RRI and open sciences research practices in the BUA to support the fair and robust selection of suitable candidates.

The project aims at the four BUA partners are:

- **Field and need assessment:** Assessment of the Status Quo including the assessment of the current structure, processes and practices of research assessments, stakeholder mapping and analyses, review of the literature, legal or internal documents, and the assessment of the relevant stakeholders perspectives and attitudes regarding the research assessment system for appointments. These aims are addressed in WP 1, WP 2, WP 3, WP 4, WP 5 and WP 7.
- **Development of an „intervention“:** comparison of “what is” with “what should” and “what could” be for each of the BUA partners. Identification of possible and likely areas of change in the administration of research assessments and governance. These aims are addressed in WP 6 and WP 7.
- **Transfer:** development of user-driven, evidence-based strategies for the implementation of research assessment reforms. These aims are addressed in WP 6 and WP 7.

- **Stakeholder engagement and Capacity building:** active engagement of relevant stakeholders in design of the project, analysis, and interpretation of results and their dissemination. It also includes activities regarding offers of low-barrier information and resources as well as knowledge transfer of good assessment practices and current developments into to the community. It addresses targeted as well as broad communities. These aims are addressed in WP 6 and WP 7.
- **Dissemination and Communication:** Continuous intramural as well as external dissemination and communication on status of the project and (preliminary) results to the scientific, administrative, as well as lay persons communities according to best practice open science practices. These aims are addressed in WP 8.

3. Description of work plan

3.1. Work packages, tasks, milestones, and deliverables

WP

WP 100 Scoping reviews

WP 110 Iterative literature review of principles of RRI research assessment including indicators, tools (scoping review)

Consolidate evidence to determine state-of-the-art criteria, tools, goals, and principles for research assessment, RRI and open science policies, especially at the level of individual researchers for purposes such as hiring, appointments, tenure track, and personnel selection.

WP 111 Development of a scoping review protocol of principles of RRI research assessment

Protocolling the objective, question, and method of the scoping review.

- ◆ Identifying review questions, inclusion criteria, and search strategy.
- ◆ Pre-specifying evidence screening and selection, data extraction, data analysis.
- ◆ Milestone: Scoping review protocol

WP 112 Scoping review of principles of RRI research assessment

Aligning the data extracted from the evidences sources with the objectives and research question of the scoping review.

- ◆ Evidence screening and selction.
 - ◆ Data extraction and analysis.
 - ◆ Deliverable: Scoping review versions 1 (initial) and 2+3 (updates)
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WP 120 Iterative literature review of implementation strategies of research assessment reforms in HEI

Consolidate evidence to determine best-practice implementation strategies of research assessment reforms in research and higher education institutions.

WP 121 Development of a scoping review protocol

Protocolling the objective, question, and method of the scoping review.

- ◆ Identifying review questions, inclusion criteria, and search strategy.
- ◆ Pre-specifying evidence screening and selection, data extraction, data analysis.
- ◆ Milestone: Scoping review protocol

WP 122 Scoping review of RRI implementation strategies

Aligning the data extracted from the evidences sources with the objectives and research question of the scoping review.

- ◆ Evidence screening and selction.
- ◆ Data extraction and analysis.
- ◆ Deliverable: Scoping review versions 1 (initial) and 2+3 (update)

WP 200 Document analysis of internal, legal and other documents

Iterative analysis of relevant documents that are updated throughout the course of the project.

WP 210 Analysis plan for document analysis

- ◆ Create analysis plan.
- ◆ Deliverable: Completed analysis plan for document analysis.

WP 220 Literature review of legal, procedural and other internal documents for appointment procedures at the BUA partners

Analysis of research assessment criteria and procedures in internal documents of the BUA partners, with a particular focus on assessment practices in appointments.

- ◆ Identifying and reviewing relevant documents from the BUA partners, especially by-laws on professorial appointments and tenure track evaluations.
 - ◆ Deliverable: Review legal/procedural overview appointments at the BUA organizations 1 (initial), 2 (update).
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WP 221 Literature review of legal and policy framework of the shared research space in Berlin

Analysis of research assessment criteria and procedures in state government documents, with a particular focus on appointment procedures.

- ◆ Review of pertinent state government documents, especially the BerLHG and current University Agreements.
- ◆ Deliverable: Review legal/policy framework of shared research space in Berlin and synthesis of findings with review on the appointment procedures of the BUA partners.

WP 300 Expert interviews

Approx. 32 semi-structured interviews with relevant actors in administration and governance at all BUA partners and the Berlin state government.

WP 310 IRB and Data Protection Plan

Developing and submitting an ethics application, which includes a data protection plan, for approval by Charité's ethics committee.

- ◆ Create IRB and data protection plan consisting of an application form, confirmation of public liability insurance, a preliminary interview guide, and a study information and consent form.
- ◆ Milestone: Accepted IRB proposal and Data protection plan for interviews.

WP 320 Analysis plan for expert interviews

Includes the research question, interview design and method of analysis.

- ◆ Create analysis plan.
- ◆ Deliverable: Completed analysis plan for expert interviews.

WP 330 Conduct and analyses of expert interviews

- ◆ Preparation: interview design and questions.
 - ◆ Participant selection and recruitment: stakeholders and experts on appointments, tenure track evaluations, and research assessments at the BUA partners and Berlin's Senate Department for Science, Health and Care (SenWGP).
 - ◆ Iterations of conducting and recording interviews, transcriptions, data analysis, and refinements.
 - ◆ Interpreting and reporting the findings in the context of implementing responsible research assessments and tenure track evaluations.
 - ◆ Deliverable: Report on expert interviews.
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WP 340 Member Checking of interview transcripts

Return of interview transcripts to interviewees to verify facts and confirm their own words.

- ◆ Give respondents notice of when they will receive the transcripts.
- ◆ Send transcripts and ask respondents to confirm accuracy and completeness of interview transcript.
- ◆ Receive feedback from respondents
- ◆ Include amended transcripts in further analysis.
- ◆ Deliverable: Report on results of entire member checking process of interview transcripts to include into final results.

WP 400 Field notes

Informal interviews, conversations, also via email, and notes on observations, context information, reflections on methods and own role as researcher during interviews.

WP 410 Analysis plan for field notes

- ◆ Create analysis plan.
- ◆ Deliverable: Completed analysis plan for field notes analyses.

WP 420 Field notes analyses

- ◆ Recording and collecting field notes throughout the entire course of the project and the research process.
- ◆ Considering and including field notes in the status quo report, the interpretation and reporting of the findings of the expert interviews and further analyses.
- ◆ Deliverable: Report on field notes analyses.

WP 500 Survey

WP 510 Addendum to the ethics application and data protection plan

- ◆ Developing and submitting an addendum to the ethics application including the online survey questions.
 - ◆ Developing and admitting data protection plan for online survey.
 - ◆ Create addendum to the ethics application and data protection plan for online survey (questions).
 - ◆ Milestone: Accepted addendum and data protection plan for interviews.
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WP 520 Analysis plan for online survey

Includes the survey questions and design and the method of analysis.

- ◆ Create analysis plan.
- ◆ Deliverable: Completed analysis plan for online survey.

WP 530 Setting up and conducting online-survey

Setting up and conducting an anonymous online-survey among broad sample including relevant actors at the BUA partners in administration and governance, as well as researchers. The survey includes both quantitative and qualitative questions and builds on the results of the scoping reviews, the analysis of legal and procedural documents, and the expert interviews.

- ◆ Preparation: develop survey questions, identify online survey tool, and create survey.
- ◆ Milestone: Completed set-up of online survey.
- ◆ Participant selection: stakeholders and experts on appointments, tenure track evaluations, and research assessments, as well as researchers at all BUA partners.
- ◆ Sending out link to survey and potential reminders to participants.
- ◆ Deliverable: Analysis and report of the findings in the context of implementing responsible research assessments and tenure track evaluations.

WP 600 Development of an “intervention” including implementation plans

This WP builds on the results of the scoping reviews, document analyses, and will also iteratively include the results from the expert interviews and the survey.

WP 610 Member checking of analyzed data

Return of analyzed data to respondents to check whether or not they can identify their experiences in the synthesized themes.

- ◆ Give respondents notice of when they will receive the data.
 - ◆ Send transcripts and ask respondents to confirm accuracy and completeness of interview transcript.
 - ◆ Receive feedback (and potentially discuss feedback with respondents).
 - ◆ Include feedback in further analysis.
 - ◆ Deliverable: Report on results of entire member checking process to include into final results.
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WP 620 Development of an “intervention”

Identification of current developments for the optimization of research evaluation as well as possible need for adaptation of the status quo together with the stakeholders.

- ◆ Iterative synthesis of the findings from the scoping reviews, document analyses, expert interviews, informal field notes, and the survey.
- ◆ Comparative analysis of status quo descriptions and current developments in responsible research assessment
- ◆ Deliverable: Status quo descriptions for each BUA partner
- ◆ Milestone: Completed workshops at each BUA partner on integrating responsible research assessment practices in existing sets of criteria, 1 (needs assessment), 2 (identification of wanted “intervention”)

WP 630 Development of an implementation strategy/plan

Bringing intervention into application by developing a plan to implement possible changes together with the relevant stakeholders at all BUA partners.

- ◆ Participatory development of a mission-oriented strategy to implement potential changes in assessment procedures.
- ◆ Deliverables: Synthesis of different strategic plans and approaches.
- ◆ Milestone: Completed workshop with relevant stakeholders from all BUA partners on respective implementation plans

WP 700 Stakeholder engagement and capacity building

WP 710 Concept on stakeholder engagement and capacity building

Concept detailing different aspects and measures of stakeholder engagement and capacity building that are planned over the course of the project.

- ◆ Create concept
- ◆ Milestone: Completed concept on stakeholder engagement and capacity building

WP 720 Stakeholder engagement

Identifying relevant stakeholders, establishing trust and a good working relationship, keeping in touch. Active engagement of relevant stakeholders at all BUA partners in design of the project, analysis, and interpretation of results and their dissemination.

- ◆ Stakeholder mapping
 - ◆ Addressing stakeholders, organizing and conducting kick-off meetings
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- ◆ Establishing regular meetings (JF) and other exchange formats
 - ◆ Finding allies who share and support the project's concerns
 - ◆ Organizing and conducting workshops and need/requirement analyses
 - ◆ Milestone: Completion of kick-off meetings at each BUA partner
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WP 721 Meeting with Equal Opportunity Officers

Presenting MAI-I to the teams of Equal Opportunity Officers at all BUA partners to establish a good and trustworthy working relationship and to try to win them as allies who spread the word and support the project's purpose and aims in different contexts of research assessment that they attend, such as appointment committees.

- ◆ Sending out meeting request, finding appointment, preparing presentation
 - ◆ Milestone: Completed meeting with Equal Opportunity Officers
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WP 730 Capacity building

Activities regarding offers of low-barrier information events and resources as well as knowledge transfer of good assessment practices and current developments into the community.

- ◆ Organizing and conducting information sessions and talks on responsible research assessment, including presentations from internal and external experts
 - ◆ Deliverable: Creation (and dissemination) of information material on responsible research assessment (slides, webinar, "Erklärvideo," etc.).
 - ◆ Milestone: Completion of information sessions for relevant actors and communities at/addressing each BUA partner, 1 (general information on responsible research assessment), 2-4 (in-depth information on particular practices), 5 (symposium on responsible research assessment)
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WP 731 Information session on Responsible Research Assessment (general) for Admin community

Information session introducing Responsible Research Assessment in a general overview (how has researched been assessed so far, why is that problematic, what are potential ways of improvement) to relevant actors in the governance and administration of appointment procedures and tenure track evaluations of all BUA partners.

- ◆ Scheduling appointment, organizing event, preparing presentation(s)
 - ◆ Milestone: Completed information session on responsible research assessment for the admin community
 - ◆ Deliverable: Report on information session on Responsible Research Assessment (general)
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WP 732 Series of in-depth information sessions on different aspects of Responsible Research Assessment

Series of in-depth information sessions on different aspects of responsible research assessment in appointment procedures and tenure track evaluations consisting of both a theoretical input and the presentation of a practical example ideally from one of the BUA partners, such as strategies to reduce the risk of unconscious bias, the concept of academic age, open science criteria, etc.

- ◆ Scheduling appointments, organizing events including invitation of potential guest speakers, preparing presentations
- ◆ Milestone: Completed Series of in-depth information sessions on different aspects of Responsible Research Assessment
- ◆ Deliverable: Report on in-depth information sessions

WP 800 Dissemination and communication

Continuous intramural as well as external dissemination and communication on status of the project and (preliminary) results to the scientific, administrative, as well as lay persons communities according to best practice open science practices.

WP 810 Set-up and maintenance of the QUEST project page

- ◆ Create and regularly update QUEST project page

WP 820 Set-up and maintenance of the OSF project page

- ◆ Create and regularly update OSF project page
- ◆ upload relevant documents including protocols and other project outputs

WP 830 Annual project presentations at conferences/meetings (focus: stakeholders)

- ◆ Deliverable: presentation slides or posters, other formats

WP 840 Communication to the public

- ◆ Deliverable: posts, interviews other formats

WP 900 Project management

WP 910 Project plan

Concept detailing the project's tasks, timeline, milestones and deliverables as well as resources and responsibilities with regard to activities, dissemination and communication.

- ◆ Deliverable: Project plan
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WP 920 Open science strategy

Concept detailing the project's open science strategy with regard to analyses plans, activities, dissemination and communication.

- ◆ Deliverable: Open science strategy

WP 930 Joint innovation group meetings

- ◆ Milestone: Project kick-off meeting
- ◆ Milestone: Project year 1 and 2 meetings
- ◆ Milestone: Project close out meeting

WP 940 General management tasks

Coordination of meetings, rooms, catering throughout the project duration

3.2. Deliverables

D1.1.0: Scoping review of principles of RRI research assessment versions 1 (initial) and 2+3 (updates)

D1.2.0: Scoping review of implementation strategies of research assessment reforms in HEI versions 1 (initial) and 2+3 (updates)

D2.1.0: Completed analysis plan for document analysis

D2.2.0: Review legal/procedural overview appointments at the BUA organizations 1 (initial), 2 (update)

D2.2.1: Review legal/policy framework of shared research space in Berlin and synthesis of findings with review on the appointment procedures of the BUA partners

D3.2.0: Completed analysis plan for expert interviews

D3.3.0: Report on expert interviews

D3.4.0: Report on results of entire member checking process of interview transcripts to include into final results

D4.1.0: Completed analysis plan for field notes analyses

D4.2.0: Report on field notes analyses

D5.1.0: Accepted addendum and data protection plan for interviews

D5.2.0: Completed analysis plan for online survey

D5.3.0: Analysis and report of the findings in the context of implementing responsible research assessments and tenure track evaluations

D6.1.0: Report on results of entire member checking process to include into final results

D6.2.0: Status quo descriptions for each BUA partner

D6.3.0: Synthesis of different strategic plans and approaches

D7.3.0: Creation (and dissemination) of information material on responsible research assessment (slides, webinar, "Erklärvideo," etc.)

- D7.3.1: Report on information session on Responsible Research Assessment (general)
- D7.3.2: Report on in-depth information sessions
- D8.3.0: Annual project presentations at conferences/meetings (focus: stakeholders)
- D8.4.0: Communication to the public
- D9.1.0: Project plan
- D9.2.0: Open science strategy

4. Relevant outputs, outcomes and impact

Outputs:

Evidence:

- Conduct of interviews: Measurement: Number of (informal) interviews with relevant actors across BUA partners and their written synthesis
- Literature Evidence-base: Measurement: number of scoping reviews with relevant questions of analyses and their synthesis

Stakeholder engagement/participation:

- Measurement: number of commented, co-written, or revised relevant documents by relevant actors across the BUA partners
- Stakeholder meetings and workshops (or similar formats): Measurement: Number of Stakeholder meetings with BUA members and their written synthesis, number of workshops or other formats with BUA members and their written synthesis

Communication and capacity building:

- Educational events, webinars, talks
- Publications, podcasts
- Support to fulfill the self-commitments associated with the signing of the "Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment" (CoARA) or other reform initiatives

Outcome

Strategy, governance:

- User-led strategy development based on findings. Measurement: number of co-created strategy documents or activities such as Beschlussvorlagen or similar types of documents

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or participation and number of presentations in events of the academic self-administration (e.g. across BUA institutions)

- Good practice guidelines for research assessment in the context of appointments and tenure track evaluations, including guidance for implementation of reforms (e.g. COARA)

Infrastructure:

- Quality-oriented, RRI and OS oriented sets of criteria and good assessment aids.

Impact

- Institutional change in current assessment practice based on implementation strategy. Measurement: number of adapted official documents, such as for example “Ordnungen”, “Kriterienkataloge” (not part of the project – longterm)

5. Time plan, resources and responsibilities

The projects funding period is 02/2023 – 10/2026.

5.1. Gantt chart

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5.2. Resources and Responsibilities

5.2.1. Team

Dr. Miriam Kip

Group and project leader

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5.2.2. Responsibilities

Work Package (WP)	Deliverable	Person(s) in charge
		Dr. Miriam Kip
WP1 Scoping Reviews	D 1.1.0 Scoping review of principles of RRI research assessment versions 1 (initial) and 2+3 (updates)	Fabian Hempel/ Dr. Deborah Jachan
	D 1.2.0 Scoping review of implementation strategies of research assessment reforms in HEI versions 1 (initial) and 2+3 (updates)	
WP2 Document analysis of internal legal and other documents	D 2.1.0 Completed analysis plan for document analysis	Fabian Hempel
	D 2.2.0 Review legal/procedural overview appointments at the BUA organisations 1 (initial), 2 (update)	
	D2.2.1: Review legal/policy framework of shared research space in Berlin and synthesis of findings with review on the appointment procedures of the BUA partners	

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WP3 Expert interviews	D 3.2.0 Completed analysis plan for expert interviews	Fabian Hempel
	D 3.3.0 Report on expert interviews	
	D. 3.4.0 Report on results of entire member checking process of interview transcripts to include into final results	
WP4 Field notes	D 4.1.0 Completed analysis plan for field notes analysis	Fabian Hempel
	D 4.2.0 Report on field notes analysis	
WP5 Survey	D 5.2.0 Completed analysis plan for online survey	Dr. Deborah Jachan
	D 5.3.0 Analysis and report of the findings in the context of implementing responsible research assessments and tenure track evaluations	
WP6 Development of an “intervention” including implementation plans	D 6.1.0 Report on results of entire member checking process to include into final results	Fabian Hempel/ Dr. Deborah Jachan
	D 6.2.0 Status quo descriptions for each BUA partner	
	D 6.3.0 Synthesis of different strategic plans and approaches	
WP7 Stakeholder engagement and capacity building	D 7.2.0 Information material on responsible research assessment	Fabian Hempel/ Dr. Deborah Jachan
	D 7.3.1 Report on information session on Responsible Research Assessment (general)	
	D. 7.3.2 Report on in-depth information sessions	
WP8 Dissemination and communication	D 8.3.0 Annual project presentations at conferences/meetings (focus: stakeholders)	Fabian Hempel/ Dr. Deborah Jachan
	D 8.4.0 Communication to the public	
WP9 Project management	D 9.1.0 Project plan	Dr. Deborah Jachan/ Fabian Hempel
	D 9.2.0 Open science strategy	

5.2.3. Authorships and contributions

All authors involved in the project analyses and results are named on manuscripts for publication or project reports according to their respective contribution.

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